

"CERAMICS FOR BONE TISSUE SCAFFOLD DESIGN: BRIDGING MULTIDISCIPLINARY CHALLENGES"

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Introduction

Bone fracture is one of the leading causes of years lived with disability for which new clinical solutions are urgently required. Multidisciplinary approaches, including optimized synthetic scaffolds for patient-specific treatment, can significantly reduce rehabilitation time and improve bone integration and biomechanical recovery, benefiting both patients and healthcare systems.

At the intersection of materials science, ceramics have shown promise in mimicking the mineral phase of bone, particularly calcium phosphate-based materials such as hydroxyapatite and/or glass ceramics, zirconia and their composites. These materials provide a beneficial environment for cellular adhesion and proliferation. However, achieving the ideal balance between mechanical strength, porosity, fluid permeability and biologic response remains a major design challenge.

This talk explores the critical challenges and opportunities in the multidisciplinary design of ceramic bone scaffolds, highlighting innovative approaches that aim to improve their performance and clinical outcome.

Materials and Methods

Advanced solutions are available for high-fidelity 3D printing of ceramic architectures that accurately predict the device's overall mechanical properties [1]; clinical image data used to understand the implant's mechanical requirements can be used to account for biomechanical compatibility for patient-specific solutions. The role of the pore size and shape in the cell differentiation process also plays a significant role in the clinical outcome of the implant, and different *in-vitro* and *in-silico* models are available [2]. Optimization of material composition and surface functionalization is also a key factor in the problem. This contribution aims to provide an overview of the interplay between the material selection, geometrical features, and response of ceramic scaffolds by means of numerical methods and experimental validations. Reference to the impact of scaffold architecture on tissue growth capability will also be made.

This work will present the objectives and the preliminary results achieved so far in the Marie Curie Doctoral Network ReBone - *End-to-end multidisciplinary optimal design for improved personalized bioactive glass/ceramic bone substitute implants*". The network aims at integrating the multidisciplinary and multifaceted problem of the scaffold design for bone critical defects with particular reference to load-bearing applications.

Results and conclusions

The progresses achieved so far from different perspectives, i.e. material design, biomechanical properties, and osteointegration, are often addressed separately, and a large margin for improvement remains to be filled [3].

Only as representative data, figure 1 shows how pore size, porosity, and strength are related to each other in triply-periodic ceramic scaffolds, Gyroid and diamond architectures are reported. The upper and lower bounds on pore spacing are reported with reference to an optimal pore size for adequate tissue size and fluid permeability.

Among others, artificial intelligence approaches (for example, machine learning or generative AI [4-5]) are suitable methods for a multidisciplinary design. To this purpose, new collaborative efforts are needed to integrate clinical image data analysis, high fidelity manufacturing processes, patient-specific multiscale models and immersive reality technologies for surgical planning.

Figure 1: Example of multiparameters relationships: pore size, pore connectivity (permeability) and mechanical strength

References

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